

EXPERIMENTAL WORK ON THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING LEXICAL MATERIAL IN ENGLISH CLASSES

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Abstract: Language is the primary means of communication, it is difficult for you to imagine the existence and development of human society. At a time of great changes in our world today, the demand for learning foreign languages is growing in our country. the study of English is very deeply rooted. At the initiative of the President, English is widely taught in all fields of education. The use of technology in the process of learning English is yielding effective results.

Keywords: Foreign language, innovative technology, technological tools, methods, techniques.

After the independence of our country, the demand for learning foreign languages has increased sharply, our country is creating wide opportunities for language learning. Today, schools have modern computers, electronic resources, access to the Internet. The use of information technologies is possible not only at various stages of schoolchildren's training, but also in regular English lessons. The introduction of computer technologies in the scheme of the traditional lesson allows the teacher to work on the computer part of the educational process, the educational process is more interesting, colorful, intense. The computer cannot replace, but only complements teachers. Computer involvement allows you to make any lesson attractive and truly modern. Completing any task, using the computer, using the lesson, creates an opportunity to increase the intensity of the lesson. Use of variable materials and operational plans help individualize

learning. It can be used at all stages of computer-based teaching: new materials, consolidation, repetition, knowledge management, and teaching of skills and abilities. At the same time, it performs various functions for the child: teachers, working tools, educational tools, learning object, cooperation group, game environment, entertainment. It helps to introduce new pedagogical technologies, for example: information and communication, computer and multimedia technologies are closely related to each other. The implementation of information technologies creates the necessary conditions for the activation of the school's educational process. Computer technology helps to reveal, preserve and develop personal qualities of students. Every subject in schools, while the English language, has always used information technologies (means of storing, processing and transmitting information) in their activities; Improving them will help to increase efficiency. Therefore, using the computer as the most perfect source of information, using a book, fountain, television, calculator, VCR, etc. Naturally, it leads to improvement of the educational process. The development of computers and software has led to the greatest ease of mastering by their undeveloped users, including preschool children. In recent years, the issue of using innovative technologies in schools has been increasingly raised.

The task of the teacher is to create practical skills with the language for each student, to choose such educational methods that allow each student to show their activity and creativity. Cooperation, the methodology of the project, modern pedagogical technologies using new information technologies, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources, taking into account the abilities of children, their level of education, their individualization will help to increase the level of knowledge. Communicative approach is a strategy that stimulates communication and aims to consciously understand the material and methods of communication with them. It is not very difficult for the user to implement a

communicative approach on the Internet. A communal task should be a problem or a question for discussion, and students can not only share information, but also evaluate it. The main criterion that distinguishes this approach from other types of activities is that students choose a language unit to express their thoughts. It is not better to use the Internet in an international approach: its purpose is to learn a foreign language and to expand their knowledge and experience. Learning foreign languages using Internet resources One of the main requirements for this is to create interaction in the lesson, which is called the usual method of interactivity. Interactivity is the organization, coordination and completion of "mutual goal achievement and the result of speech means". Training with a real language, the Internet helps in the formation of skills and abilities, as well as a real interest in learning vocabulary and grammar and, therefore, is considered effective. Interactivity not only creates real life situations, but also forces students to adequately respond through foreign languages. One of the technologies that offer private lessons is the project method, a way to develop creativity, cognitive activity, and independence. The typology of projects is different. In actual practice, it should deal with mixed projects with various scientific-research, creative, application-oriented and informational features. The work of the project is a multi-level approach to learning the language of reading, auditing, speaking and grammar. The method of the project greatly contributes to the development of active independent thoughts in students. In my opinion, preparing projects teaches children to cooperate, and preparing cooperation raises mutual support and creative abilities. At the same time, the essence of innovative education in learning the English language is that the educational process involves almost all students in the learning process, and the use of new pedagogical technologies increases the quality of the lesson. For example, if we look at the pad technologies below. "Carousel" technology. Like many innovative technologies, the carousel was borrowed. Children like this work, usually a lot. Two rings are formed: inner

and outer. On the outer side of the inner ring are motionless students, on the outer side rotating every 30 seconds. Thus, they have time to speak for a few minutes and try to convince the interlocutor that they are on their right. Dialogues of a Laoretic nature are perfectly applicable, the topic is dating, nationality, conversation in a public place, etc. The guys talk excitedly, the profession is dynamic and efficient. "Theatre" technology. Something like a spectrum where you participate as viewers, experts, critics, and analysts. A few students act out the situation in the circle, the rest are observed and analyzed. It is the audience's task to tell their conclusions based on the relevant mood, emotion, character and the audience, based on what they have followed. "Sociological survey" technology. It involves children moving through the account to collect information on the proposed topic as they move. Each participant receives a list with a list of tasks. The teacher helps to formulate questions and answers, ensures that the interaction begins with English. "Proposal in progress" technology. Children are invited to read the unfinished sentence and continue it with any word that comes to mind. Proposals start out pretty vague, so guys have almost limitless options to complete it. They relate to different areas of life and can cover any topics. "Group story" technology. It is done in two ways. In the first method, each student adds one sentence to the already started story. At a certain signal (after one minute), a sheet with an unfinished story is sent in the merge. The second method is well suited for the development of the topic. The teacher asks questions in a certain order, each participant of the process writes the answer, no one can see it, and helps the neighbor. The movement takes place in a circle. So you get a few surprises at the end. "Do you believe that..." technology This type of language practice can be used on any topic. And the student is first invited to "trust" the teacher, and then get acquainted with their statements within a certain topic. "Brain loop" technology. Perfect for classrooms - universal collections of studied materials. The content of the types can be completely different and these sections

include vocabulary, grammar, reading, listening and writing. This technology requires serious. Which includes: formalizing the task, creating a presentation, thinking about focus questions, answers and answers, diplomas. At the beginning of the game, there is a selection of the jury, a competition for students to participate. Each round lasts 3 minutes, after which the answers are submitted to a panel of judges. The correctness of the answers is checked and discussed after each round, and then a series of questions are also asked to bring the teams extra points.

Conclusion

In conclusion As a result of using innovative methods in English language classes, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to give quick and correct answers is formed. Such methods make students eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process.

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